
Intersectionality of Human-Centered Design and Neocolonialism

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Abstract

The advancement of human-centred design and its growing relevance in today's society has been crucial in addressing the needs of users and fostering inclusive innovation. However, it is hard to deny that there are some underlying power dynamics and cultural biases prevalent during the process of designing systems. This paper aims at examining this particular intersectionality and its subsequent relationship between human-centred design(HCD) and neocolonialism. Drawing on critical analysis, case studies and qualitative research, this research investigates how HCD, despite its intentions for inclusivity, can inadvertently perpetuate neocolonial structures, particularly in the context of global technology and development initiatives. Through a lens of postcolonial theory and critical design studies, it reveals the subtle imposition of Western ideologies, dominant perspectives, and market-driven agendas under the guise of user-centered designs. The findings underline the need for designers, practitioners, and stakeholders to adopt reflexive strategies, acknowledge diverse worldviews, and recalibrate HCD frameworks to foster authentic empowerment and reduce the perpetuation of neocolonialism in design.

Keywords: human-centered design, neocolonialism, service design, design thinking, post-colonial theory

1. Introduction

Human-Centered Design (HCD) stands as a key aspect in design methodologies, celebrated for its emphasis on empathy, user engagement, and problem-solving. Originating from a desire to address user needs directly, it has become a big part in various industries, promising innovation that caters to diverse populations. However, beneath this seemingly altruistic surface lies a complex picture with cultural biases and power dynamics that reflect and perpetuate neocolonial structures.

In recent years, a critical lens has been turned towards HCD, unveiling inherent limitations within its frameworks. While purporting to be universally inclusive, HCD practices often emanate from a predominantly Western-centric viewpoint.

This research explores the entanglement of Human-Centered Design (HCD) practices with neocolonial structures, and looking through the inherent subtle power dynamics, cultural biases, and influences embedded within design frameworks. By analysing scholarly discussions and empirical evidence, this paper seeks to shed light on the nuanced intersections between HCD and neocolonialism, advocating for a reimagining of design processes that challenge dominant narratives and foster inclusivity, equity, and cultural sensitivity within the field.

2. Understanding Human-Centered Design (HCD)

2.1 Principles of HCD

Human-Centered Design (HCD) embodies a design approach that prioritises the needs, behaviours, and preferences of end-users throughout the design process. At its very core, HCD aims to incorporate empathy, inclusivity, and innovation by deeply understanding and addressing user concerns step-by-step. The principles of HCD revolve around empathising with users, defining their needs, ideating innovative solutions, prototyping to visualise ideas, and testing these prototypes in real user contexts. Its intended goals are noble: to create solutions that genuinely resonate with diverse user populations, ultimately leading to products, services, or systems that are more usable, effective, and impactful.

2.2 Limitations and Criticisms of Traditional HCD

Despite its proclaimed user-centric nature, traditional HCD methodologies have faced valid criticisms regarding their limitations and Western-centric biases. Most system models, for example, environmentally sustainable housing that works in European or American landscapes, need not necessarily have the same impact, or rather have opposite of the desired effects in the sub-tropical climate, while simultaneously holding that as the standard of development.^[1] These cultural specificities are embedded within HCD, highlighting its roots in Western design philosophies and methodologies.^[2] This cultural bias can lead to solutions that could potentially fail to adequately address the needs and nuances of non-Western or other marginalised communities, challenging the assumption of universality.

3. Neocolonial Tendencies in Design Practices

3.1 Defining Neocolonialism

Neocolonialism is defined as “the continued exercise of political or economic influence over a society in the absence of formal political control”.^[3] In the field of design, it represents the perpetuation of historical power structures and cultural dominance in contemporary design practices. It reflects the continuation of colonial ideologies and influences in the design process, wherein dominant cultural perspectives and power imbalances persistently shape and impact design decisions. It is also important to keep in mind that any form of colonialism also has impacts on environmental, social, political and economic aspects of a region.

Looking deeper into history and present day circumstances, instances of neocolonialism provide tangential social “benefits”, such as in the creation of schools in underprivileged regions. However, it's important to consider the hidden costs that come with these indirect "benefits." For example,

when schools are built as a result of neocolonialism, the way things are taught might be more in line with the beliefs and ideas of the ones who built the schools, not necessarily reflecting what the local indigenous people of the land truly value or believe in. Even though it might seem like a good thing on the surface, this can actually have negative effects on the communities involved. When education doesn't respect or include the culture, customs, or beliefs of a community, it can lead to the erasure of that community's identity, replacing it with a version imposed by outsiders. These problems show that neocolonialism, despite claiming to bring progress, often ends up forcing its ways rather than truly empowering communities.^[4] The sad truth is that this is an ongoing issue that is seldom brought to the forefront. Its impact reverberates through design processes, often overshadowing or dismissing diverse cultural perspectives and enhancing existing power asymmetries.

3.2 Critical Analysis of Design's Role in Neocolonialism

The story of the schools in the 'Global South' is unfortunately just one example. There has always been a paradox between the ideas of "development" and what it means for different nations. The term 'global north' and 'global south' in itself speaks for the way countries are categorised by international bodies. The Democratic Republic of Congo is a country that is extremely abundant in natural resources, like cobalt, lithium, diamonds and copper. These elements also are key components in the development of batteries and electric vehicles. In contrast, they have unfortunately been subjected to imperialistic socio-political situations exerted by the 'Global North' completely exploiting the people and the land for the sake of development of the Western and developed countries. Global technology initiatives often championed as vehicles for progress can paradoxically perpetuate Western-centric ideologies, marginalising local contexts and perspectives.

A study by the computer science researcher, Lilly Irani, offers an interesting perspective on design and development.

The Silicon Valley imaginaries of innovation position designers as producers of the new for a world positioned as already behind. This is the arrangement signified by "Designed by Apple in California. Assembled in China". These "neocolonial geographies of center and periphery" builds on older geographies of modernity and modernisation, developing and developed, extracting and extracted." (Irani, Silberman, 2016)

These patterns of consumerism also reflect on the lens through which different countries are viewed.^[5] Assembling in China requires manpower, labour and consequent environmental impacts of production. Yet, in regards to environmental debates, what often fails to be considered is that the reason India and China are the primary emitters of air pollutants, flow of world economy and goods production are largely based in this region.^[6]

4. Case Studies and Qualitative Research

I was privileged to work with tribal(indigenous) communities of Kerala, a state in South India. It is estimated that there are around 4 million tribal people living in various mountainous parts of the state.^[7] Despite being indigenous to the land, British occupation of India led to the forceful displacement of these communities which led to settler colonialism. This led to schemes of social activism and the implementation of service design schemes in the region align with the modern ideas of development. There are schemes which promoted the youth of the community to go for construction and labour intensive jobs, in a way of gathering cheap labour for the adjacent cities. Albeit coming from the intentions of empowering the community to earn, rather than live off the

indigenous land and practice the century long traditions, what it has done is fragmenting the culture of the people.

One Laptop Per Child(OLPC) is a worldwide program that aimed at providing low-cost laptops to children of developing countries. The project has been described as a “parachute” effort where “cultural disconnects kept kids from benefitting from the machines” (“Peru’s One Laptop Per Child” 2012). The initiative overlooked necessary elements like information access, political landscape and e-waste due to the low quality which would have provided the OLPC creators with the insight to make their product culturally relevant. "The laptop was subsequently not embraced by or useful to the communities it intended to serve. Unfortunately, OLPC exemplifies the design neocolonialism that occurs frequently when designers attempt to change situations they do not sufficiently understand, or are not able to know if they sufficiently understand. [8]" (Janzer, Weinstein, 2014)

5. Conclusion

Towards a Decolonised Approach in Design

Elizabeth Tunstall’s *Decolonising Design*, have several insights I personally find crucial. Prioritising inclusivity, cultural sensitivity, and equitable partnerships with marginalised communities, can all go a long way in establishing global security. Acknowledging the existence of the influence of neocolonialism and incorporating indigenous knowledge and diverse cultural narratives become integral to authentic inclusivity and equality in design frameworks. While technological and modern design advancements are necessary in today’s society, it would go a long way if the perspectives of the native people of the land are taken into account and design solutions are tailored keeping these in mind.

References

- [1] Fry, T. (2011). Design as politics. Berg.
- [2] Fry, T. (2008). Design futuring: Sustainability, Ethics and new practice. Bloomsbury visual arts.
- [3] Ritzer, G. (2007). Blackwell Reference Online.
- [4] Janzer, C. L., & Weinstein, L. S. (2014). Social Design and Neocolonialism. *Design and Culture*, 6(3), 327–343. <https://doi.org/10.2752/175613114x14105155617429>
- [5] Irani, L. C., & Silberman, M. S. (2016). Stories we tell about labor. *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2858036.2858592>

[6] Chakrabarty, D. (2018). Planetary crises and the difficulty of being modern. *Millennium: Journal of International Studies*, 46(3), 259–282. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305829818771277>

[7] *Adiyan*. KIRTADS. (n.d.). <https://kirtads.kerala.gov.in/tribals-in-kerala/>

[8] Janzer, C. L., & Weinstein, L. S. (2014). Social Design and Neocolonialism. *Design and Culture*, 6(3), 327–343. <https://doi.org/10.2752/175613114x14105155617429>

[9] OpenAI. (2023). *ChatGPT* (Nov 21 version) [Large language model]. <https://chat.openai.com>
-Prompts

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